

1 **From linear to circular integrated waste**
2 **management systems: a review of**
3 **methodological approaches**

4 *Selene Cobo^a, Antonio Dominguez-Ramos^b and Angel Irabien^c*

5 ^{a,b,c}Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, University of Cantabria,

6 Avda. los Castros s.n., Santander, 39005, Spain

7 ^a**Corresponding Author. Tel.: +34 942 20 09 31. E-mail: cobos@unican.es**

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15 ABSTRACT

16 The continuous depletion of natural resources related to our lifestyle cannot be sustained
17 indefinitely. Two major lines of action can be taken to overcome this challenge: the application
18 of waste prevention policies and the shift from the classical linear Integrated Waste
19 Management Systems (IWMSs) that focus solely on the treatment of Municipal Solid Waste
20 (MSW) to circular IWMSs (CIWMSs) that combine waste and materials management,
21 incentivizing the circularity of resources. The system analysis tools applied to design and assess
22 the performance of linear IWMSs were reviewed in order to identify the weak spots of these
23 methodologies, the difficulties of applying them to CIWMSs, and the topics that could benefit
24 from further research and standardization. The findings of the literature review provided the
25 basis to develop a methodological framework for the analysis of CIWMSs that relies on the
26 expansion of the typical IWMS boundaries to include the upstream subsystems that reflect the
27 transformation of resources and its interconnections with the waste management subsystems.
28 *Keywords:* integrated waste management systems, circular economy, waste prevention,
29 resource recovery, systems thinking, life cycle assessment

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32 **1. Introduction**

33

34 Resources within planet Earth are finite by nature. Natural resources whose formation roots
35 in other geologic periods, like mineral deposits, cannot be renewed in human timescales and
36 thus their reservoirs are bound to eventually become depleted if their consumption continues
37 (Prior et al., 2012; Shafiee and Topal, 2009). On the other hand, natural stocks subject to
38 biological cycles (a population of trees for example) yield a sustainable flow of valuable goods
39 and services (such as wood and CO₂ removal from the atmosphere) on a continuous basis
40 (Costanza and Daly, 1992). Nonetheless, since the early 1970s some renewable natural
41 resources are being exploited faster than they can be renewed (Borucke et al., 2013). As a
42 matter of fact, it would take 1.64 planets to regenerate in one year the natural resources
43 consumed in 2016 (Global footprint network, 2016). This figure is expected to worsen because
44 of the projected population increase and the improved acquisition levels of the emerging
45 economies (Foley et al., 2011; Karak et al., 2012).

46

47 If the consumption of raw materials rises, so does waste generation (Shahbazi et al., 2016).
48 Around 1.3 billion tons of MSW are annually produced in cities all over the world (Hoornweg
49 and Bhada-Tata, 2012), and a significant amount of the waste produced in low and lower-
50 middle income countries is disposed of in open dumps (Hoornweg and Bhada-Tata, 2012)
51 lacking measures to prevent safety and environmental hazards. Under the assumption that every
52 ton of MSW generated in cities worldwide could be stored in 1 m³ of sanitary landfill (Li et al.,
53 2013), a landfill volume equivalent to that of 347,000 Olympic swimming pools would be
54 required every year. Accordingly, policies against landfills are mostly motivated by a lack of
55 space, particularly in the highly populated areas of Europe and Asia, where landfills are more
56 likely to interfere with other land uses like agriculture (Moh and Abd Manaf, 2014).

57

58 In fact, waste valorization might help to overcome one of the most pressing global
59 challenges: securing the food supply. Waste has been suggested as a plausible source to recover
60 phosphorus (Reijnders, 2014; Tarayre et al., 2016; Withers et al., 2015), an essential nutrient
61 to the metabolism of plants and by extension to agriculture, whose remaining accessible
62 reserves could run out as soon as 50 years from now (Gilbert, 2009).

63

64 Hence, as the principles of industrial ecology dictate, resources and waste management are
65 key to meeting the future needs of society in a sustainable manner. Waste prevention activities
66 or policies such as restricting planned obsolescence in electronic products and measures like
67 minimizing product weight or design for disassembly (Li et al., 2015) will contribute to tackle
68 these issues.

69

70 A reduction in the consumption of natural resources and the amount of waste generated
71 would also be accomplished if a shift to circular economic and production systems, mimicking
72 the self-sustaining closed loop systems found in nature, such as the water cycle, was put into
73 practice. A circular economy aims at transforming waste back into a resource, by reversing the
74 dominant linear trend of extracting, processing, consuming or using and then disposing of raw
75 materials, with the ultimate goal of preserving natural resources while maintaining the
76 economic growth and minimizing the environmental impacts (Ghisellini et al., 2016; Lieder
77 and Rashid, 2016).

78

79 In a circular economy the reduction in the environmental impacts, such as global warming,
80 is due to the improvement in resource and energy efficiencies. For instance, it has been

81 demonstrated that the production of secondary aluminum from scrap consumes less than 5%
82 of the energy needed in the production of primary aluminum (JRC, 2014); this entails that the
83 emission of up to 19 tons of equivalent CO₂ to the atmosphere could be avoided per ton of
84 aluminum that is recycled instead of produced from the mineral ore (Damgaard et al., 2009).

85

86 Given all the benefits that the circularity of resources has to offer, the reasonable question to
87 pose is how society and industry can successfully transition to a circular economy. The
88 straightforward answer from an engineering point of view is through the design of efficient
89 CIWMSs that link resource processing and waste treatment, and allow the potential of waste
90 to be fully exploited. A CIWMS is expected to produce not only materials, but also energy and
91 nutrients; additionally, it could deliver certain chemicals.

92

93 Therefore, a trade-off between the functions of a CIWMS is unavoidable. A thorough
94 analysis must be carried out prior to the design stage of a CIWMS so that it can assist in the
95 decision-making process. As the analytical framework supported by systems thinking can
96 provide a holistic view on the sustainability challenges that arise from the interconnections
97 between the components of an IWMS (Chang et al., 2011; Singh et al., 2014), so far manifold
98 papers applying a systems-oriented approach to waste management have been published.

99

100 That is the reason only the most recent papers focusing on the analysis of IWMSs have been
101 addressed in this study. The aim of this paper is to conduct a critical and comprehensive review
102 of the studies published since 2011 that analyze IWMSs whose input is MSW, in order to gain
103 insight into the strengths and shortcomings of the methodologies currently being applied, and
104 to identify their applicability to a sustainable CIWMS targeting resource recovery. To the best

105 of the authors' knowledge, an IWMS has never been analyzed from the perspective of a circular
106 economy before. The novelty of this review is that the characteristics of a CIWMS are defined,
107 the potential pitfalls of applying the current methodologies deployed in the analysis of linear
108 IWMSs to a CIWMS are identified and possible methodological improvements are proposed.

109

110 This review is structured as follows: first, the methodology applied in the selection of the
111 reviewed papers is described. Second the state-of-the-art technologies and processes for
112 IWMSs are outlined, along with their potential restraints to the development of a circular
113 economy. Third, the characteristics of a CIWMS are defined. Next, the methodologies
114 currently applied to analyze IWMSs are briefly described and the hottest topics regarding the
115 methodological aspects of the analysis of IMWSs are subsequently identified. Finally, the
116 conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are summarized, with special emphasis on
117 the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology.

118

119

120 **2. Method**

121

122 77 papers analyzing IWMSs that treat MSW and published after 2010 were identified by
123 means of the Scopus database (Scopus, 2016). They are listed in Appendix A. The systematic
124 review method was conducted applying four different keyword strings: i) *municipal solid*
125 *waste, integrated, system and analysis*, ii) *municipal solid waste, integrated, system and*
126 *methodology*, iii) *municipal solid waste, integrated, system and (sustainable or sustainability)*.
127 The papers focusing on the analysis of scenarios regarding alternative waste treatment
128 technologies or processes were excluded from the review.

129

130 Once the technological obstacles faced by CIWMSs and the limitations of the methodologies
131 applied for the analysis of IWMSs were detected in the reviewed studies, the search criteria
132 were expanded to cover the specific topics of interest. Those additional papers are listed
133 throughout the document.

134

135

136 **3. Technological background**

137

138 Prior to the proposal of guidelines for the analysis of CIWMSs that enhance the circularity
139 of resources and enable the transition to a circular economy, it is mandatory to recognize the
140 technological restrictions to the implementation of such a system. They are outlined in this
141 section.

142

143 *3.1. Quality and value of recycled materials*

144 The market penetration of recycled materials is highly dependent on their physical and
145 chemical characteristics, which will determine their price. However, not all the existing
146 recycling technologies enable a fair competition between virgin and secondary materials,
147 because their quality might differ.

148

149 Recycling technologies either downgrade or upgrade the materials in respect to the quality
150 of the virgin materials. Downgrading implies that the properties of the recycled material are
151 not as good as those of the virgin material. Instead, upgrading technologies improve the quality
152 of the waste materials at least up to the quality of the virgin materials.

153

154 In closed-loop recycling, the material is recycled into the same product system and the
155 inherent properties of the recycled material are maintained virtually identical to those of the
156 virgin material. Oppositely, in open-loop recycling the material is recycled into a different
157 product system and its inherent properties may or may not differ to those of the virgin material
158 (ISO 14044, 2006). Closed-loop recycling is not equivalent to infinite recycling; materials can
159 be used and later recycled within a closed-loop system for a number of times, until
160 microstructural changes in the material or the accumulation of chemical elements and
161 compounds hamper its further reuse (Gaustad et al., 2011).

162

163 A case of closed-loop recycling occurs when a glass bottle is recycled into a glass jar, because
164 the glass jar could be recycled back into a glass bottle with the same functionality as the original
165 one (Haupt et al., 2017a), whereas recycling PET bottles into PET fibers is an example of open-
166 loop recycling (Shen et al., 2010); it is an irreversible process.

167

168 Recycling processes can be further classified as downcycling or upcycling processes.
169 Downcycling has been defined as the recycling of materials into lower value products (Gaustad
170 et al, 2012). The use of wrought scrap in cast products, due to their ability to accommodate
171 higher silicon contamination, is considered downcycling. On the contrary, if the waste
172 materials are recycled into products of higher value, the recycling process is called upcycling
173 (Pol, 2010). Upcycling involves a change in the fundamental properties of the material, like its
174 physical structure or its chemical composition. Novel approaches to upcycling described in the
175 literature entail chemical (Pol, 2010; Zhuo et al., 2012) or biological transformation (Kenny et
176 al., 2008). Figure 1 compiles the types of recycling processes according to the quality of the

177 recycled materials and the value of the resulting recycled products in respect to the original
 178 materials and products.

179

180 **Figure 1.** Classification of recycling processes (*1.5-column fitting image*)

181 Although downgrading and upgrading are often used as synonyms of downcycling and
 182 upcycling, Figure 1 shows that is not necessarily true: a waste material may be upgraded to
 183 maintain its original function, and later used to manufacture a product of lower value than the
 184 original one. The confusion regarding the terminology has recently been intensified by Geyer
 185 et al. (2016), who question the usefulness of making a distinction between open and closed-
 186 loop recycling.

187

188 *3.2. State-of-the-art technologies and processes for IWMSs*

189 Regarding the technical and economic factors that hinder the complete separation and
 190 recycling of materials (O'Connor et al., 2016; Ciacci et al., 2015; Reuter, 2011), the
 191 concentration of the valuable materials in the discarded products and wastes is one of the

192 critical parameters that will determine the feasibility of the recovery process (Johnson et al.,
193 2007); several authors agree that the *unrecyclability* of some materials stems from the
194 combination of small quantities of multiple materials in one product, like a smartphone (Reck
195 and Graedel, 2012; Chancerel et al., 2013). Hence the need to design systems that contemplate
196 the valorization of all the materials within a given product. Clearly, the solution to this
197 challenge relies on the development of more efficient sorting and disassembly technologies,
198 along with the implementation of policies that promote the separate collection of these wastes.

199

200 One strategy that has been proposed to tackle the limitations of the current recycling
201 technologies is to store in landfills the waste that cannot be properly separated or recycled until
202 the pertinent technologies have been developed up to the point that they enable the recovery of
203 the remaining secondary raw materials in waste (Bosmans et al., 2013), which is the prime
204 purpose of landfill mining, along with energy recovery from the stored waste (Jones et al.,
205 2013). Although several environmental and economic assessments of landfill mining have been
206 performed so far (Danthurebandara et al., 2015; Laner et al., 2016; Van Passel et al., 2013),
207 more applied research is needed before the most sustainable pathway to landfill mining is
208 agreed upon (Krook et al., 2012).

209

210 Even though recycling efficiencies reached their full potential in the future, MSW is a
211 complex heterogeneous mix of materials, and that prevents it from being treated by a single
212 technology (Arena, 2015). **It is important to make a distinction between waste treatment,**
213 **that is to say, the set of processes seeking to minimize the environmental impacts of waste**
214 **in order to comply with the pertinent regulations, and waste valorization, which concerns**
215 **the transformation of waste into a product capable of providing society with a valuable**

216 **service. However, a given waste management system can provide both functions, that is**
217 **to say, waste treatment and waste valorization.**

218

219 A MSW management system focused on valorization must include a subsystem for materials
220 sorting. The paper, cardboard, plastics, glass, aluminum and iron present in MSW are usually
221 sorted in material recovery facilities and sent to recycling industries, where they are upgraded
222 to be reintroduced into the market. For further information about the quality of recyclables and
223 their recovery efficiencies in commingled and single-stream waste, the reader should refer to
224 Cimpan et al. (2015). There are several options for the valorization of both the inorganic and
225 organic remaining materials. The alternative treatments to recycling the inorganic fraction of
226 waste such as leftover plastic or textiles are the waste-to-energy processes like incineration,
227 gasification or pyrolysis; the most developed and widespread of which is incineration (Arena,
228 2012). These thermochemical processes can also be applied to the organic fraction of waste.
229 The biological processes of anaerobic digestion and composting enable the organic matter to
230 be looped back into the system as fertilizer (digestate or compost) (Brändli et al., 2007), so
231 they could be considered recycling processes. In fact, anaerobic digestion is a strategy to
232 simultaneously recover nutrients from the solid digestate and energy from the biogas produced
233 by the microorganisms (Sawatdeenarunat et al., 2016).

234

235 Furthermore, new processes to valorize the organic fraction of waste are being proposed. The
236 fermentation of organic waste has been suggested as a method to produce hydrogen (Poggi-
237 Varaldo et al., 2014). Another example is the enzymatic liquefaction process proposed to
238 separate the solid non-degradable materials that can be upgraded to Refuse Derived Fuel from
239 a bioliquid that can be digested to produce biogas (Tonini and Astrup, 2012). In addition to

240 those, a number of processes to produce valuable chemicals such as levulinic acid (Sadhukhan
241 et al., 2016) from organic waste or Refuse Derived Fuel have arisen; these are upcycling
242 processes that fall within the category of waste refineries. Several authors propose to gasify
243 waste in order to obtain syngas, a precursor to either the catalytic synthesis of methanol or the
244 production of hydrocarbons via the Fischer Tropsch process (Lavoie, et al., 2013; Niziolek et
245 al., 2015; Niziolek et al., 2017; Pressley et al., 2014) Of the above-mentioned processes, the
246 only one at large scale is operated by the company Enerkem, with a production capacity of
247 38,000 m³ of methanol per year (Enerkem, 2017).

248

249 *3.3. Materials recycling or energy recovery?*

250 In the specific case wherein the current state of the technologies allows a residual material to
251 undergo either a recycling or an energy recovery process, materials recovery is usually
252 encouraged; the Waste Framework Directive (EP and EC, 2008) states that, unless adequately
253 justified by LCA, the EU Member States must follow the waste management hierarchy,
254 according to which materials recycling takes precedence over energy recovery.

255

256 However, whereas the vast majority of studies agree that landfill is the least desired waste
257 management alternative from an environmental point of view (Belboom et al., 2013; Coventry
258 et al., 2016; Eriksson et al., 2005; Erses Yay, 2015; Fiorentino et al., 2015; Manfredi et al.,
259 2011; Tulokhonova and Ulanova, 2013), and there is also consensus on the claim that waste
260 prevention and re-use are the cleanest and most efficient policies, the performed literature
261 review reveals an ongoing debate on the final destination of the recyclable fractions of waste
262 (Blengini et al., 2012; Consonni et al., 2011; Merrild et al., 2012): should they be reintroduced
263 into the production cycles, as new products or compost, or be sent to energy recovery facilities?

264 The answer will greatly depend on the composition of the waste stream, which will determine
265 its heating value and thus, its energy recovery potential. Furthermore, the assumptions made in
266 the analysis, the system boundaries set and the local characteristics of the specific case study,
267 will determine the optimal valorization strategy.

268

269 Cossu (2014) analyzed the reasons behind the promotion of recycling. It causes the
270 preservation of natural resources inasmuch as they are being extracted to a lesser degree.
271 Moreover, a reduction in the amount of waste that needs to be properly managed or disposed
272 of gives rise to cost savings in treatment processes. Nevertheless, **the assumption that the**
273 **economic costs and environmental impacts of material recycling are lower than those**
274 **related to the extraction and processing of the virgin raw materials cannot be**
275 **substantiated without a thorough analysis.**

276

277 In the context of a globalized market, one of the factors that play a key role to the detriment
278 of materials recycling is the long transport distances that they must go through to reach their
279 end-users (Merrild et al., 2012), which has both environmental and economic drawbacks.
280 Additionally, Massarutto et al. (2011) proved that if a critical recycling rate (the ratio between
281 the recycled materials and the waste generated) is exceeded, the economic benefits from
282 recycling do not compensate its costs. Their study was based on the assumption that the quality
283 of the collected materials worsens as the separation levels (the ratio between the source
284 separated waste and the total amount of generated waste) increase, which was verified with
285 data from waste management systems.

286

287 Several other authors have emphasized the importance of assessing the effect of increasing
288 the recycling rates on the quality of the materials (Arena and Di Gregorio, 2014; Cossu, 2014;
289 Haupt, et al., 2017b; Rigamonti et al., 2009). Some studies concluded that higher separation
290 levels are not indicative of better materials quality (Consonni and Viganò, 2011; Rigamonti et
291 al., 2009). On the contrary, systems focusing on quality rather than on quantity are likely to
292 outperform the others.

293

294 An example of the damaging effects of recycling can be found in the steel manufacturing
295 industry. The increased use of secondary materials in the steel making process causes an
296 accumulation of elements such as copper, which hardens steel decreasing its quality and
297 making it necessary to dilute the amount of recycled scrap (Haupt et al., 2017b). The counter-
298 effect of dilution is that it reduces the market demand for recyclables (Modaresi and Müller,
299 2012). Hence, as Loughlin and Barlaz (2006) pointed out, recycling policies must make sure
300 that the supply of recycled materials matches the demand.

301

302 Particular attention must be paid to the potential hazards of recycling because of human
303 exposure to pollutants and toxic compounds. Bisphenol A was found in an array of waste paper
304 samples, possibly as a consequence of the recycling of secondary waste paper (Pivnenko et al.,
305 2015). Recycling has also been recently pointed as a potential source of phthalates in plastics
306 (Pivnenko et al., 2016); as a consequence, the application of recycled plastics in products
307 sensitive to phthalate content, such as toys and food packaging, must be restricted.

308

309 The risk for human health is in fact the main argument that the detractors of energy recovery
310 technologies hold, despite the fact that the thermochemical processes and anaerobic digestion

311 are a means to simultaneously reduce the volume and mass of solid waste and produce heat
312 and electricity. Incineration has been traditionally regarded by the public opinion as a threat to
313 human health and the environment, because of the high concentrations of heavy metals, dioxins
314 and furans present in the flue gases prior to the development of the current sophisticated Air
315 Pollution Control Systems (Brunner and Rechberger, 2015). However, with the state-of-the art
316 technologies, these pollutants do not pose a risk any longer, since they are well below the air
317 emission limit values established by the European legislation, which are quite restrictive in
318 comparison to those of other countries (Vehlow, 2015)

319

320 Furthermore, several studies report that savings on the environmental impacts can be
321 achieved displacing conventional energy sources by MSW (Boesch et al., 2014; Fruergaard
322 and Astrup, 2011). Hence the importance of linking the analysis of the energy and waste
323 management systems (Juul et al., 2013), as Eriksson and Bisailon (2011) and Münster et al.
324 (2015) did.

325

326 The competition between materials recycling and energy recovery is of particular interest for
327 those materials such as cardboard and plastic with high calorific values (Merrild et al., 2012),
328 which make them attractive fuels for heat and electricity production, whereas deliberately
329 subjecting the incombustible materials, i.e. metals and glass, to energy recovery processes
330 seems pointless. However, a fraction of the metals that cannot be separated by mechanical and
331 magnetic methods can be recovered after the incineration process, because of their enhanced
332 concentration in the residual ash (Cossu and Williams, 2015).

333

334 Taking into account all the considerations described above, it is reasonable to conclude that
335 **materials recycling and energy recovery should complement each other to meet the local**
336 **demands; even in the utopian scenario wherein it is technologically and economically**
337 **feasible to completely close the material loops, there might still be a demand for virgin**
338 **materials, not only because of their higher quality, but also because of social objections.**

339

340

341 **4. Framework for the analysis of CIWMSs**

342

343 The precise definition of a CIWMS is instrumental to the development of a framework that
344 relies on that concept. The previously discussed barriers to the development of CIWMSs should
345 provide a basis for the delimitation of their system boundaries and the definition of their
346 functions. These notions, which are based on the principles of the cradle-to-cradle design
347 (McDonough and Braungart, 2002), are explored to a greater extent in this section.

348

349 *4.1. Previous application of the circular economy approach to the design of IWMSs*

350 Although specific guidelines for the design and assessment of CIWMSs from a systems
351 perspective have not been found in the literature, Arena and Di Gregorio (2014) proposed a
352 series of principles, consistent with the targets of the circular economy, that IWMSs should
353 follow: “An integrated and sustainable waste management system should be defined and
354 developed according to the following criteria: i) to minimize use of landfills and ensure that no
355 landfilled waste is biologically active or contains mobile hazardous substances (...); ii) to
356 minimize operations that entail excessive consumption of raw materials and energy without
357 yielding an overall environmental advantage; iii) to maximize recovery of materials, albeit in

358 respect of the previous point; and iv) to maximize energy recovery for materials that cannot
359 be efficiently recycled, in order to save both landfill volumes and fossil-fuel resources”.

360

361 *4.2. Proposed definition*

362 A description of the concepts of IWMSs and CIWMSs is provided in this section. **An IWMS**
363 **denotes a system whose main input is waste and comprises a number of processes to sort**
364 **this waste and give each waste fraction the most appropriate treatment according to its**
365 **chemical composition and the desired function of the system outputs.** However, this
366 definition corresponds to that of a linear IWMS, like the one shown in Figure 2. If an IWMS
367 is to be studied from the perspective of a circular economy and waste prevention, this definition
368 is incomplete. **A CIWMS is a type of IWMS that seeks to enhance the circularity of**
369 **resources by strengthening the link between waste treatment and resource recovery.**
370 Thus, **CIWMSs can be considered an instrument that enables to fulfill the goals of a**
371 **circular economy.** The definition of CIWMSs could also apply to a system that focuses on
372 just one waste fraction, such as organic waste.

373

374 **The purpose of a sustainable CIWMS is to achieve the maximum economic profit and**
375 **benefits for society at the expense of the minimum environmental impacts and**
376 **consumption of natural resources.** Under this perspective, materials upcycling is favored
377 over downcycling. To accomplish these sustainability goals, the maximum amount of waste is
378 expected to be valorized to expand its lifetime, so that it can serve a function to society. This
379 entails that the amount of waste sent to landfill is minimized, although landfills cannot be
380 totally replaced (Cossu, 2012) because all the other subsystems generate certain amount of
381 waste that the current technologies cannot valorize.

382

383

Figure 2. Linear IWMS (2-column fitting image)

384

385 A CIWMS can be as complicated as the designers wish, but **a CIWMS that manages mixed**
 386 **MSW would ideally deliver materials, energy and nutrients. It could also supply some**
 387 **chemicals**, a relatively novel approach to waste management. The waste refinery concept,
 388 analogous to that of an oil refinery but taking waste as a feedstock, has gained popularity in
 389 recent years (Richards and Taherzadeh, 2015). **A waste refinery is a type of IWMSs wherein**
 390 **chemical reactions take place to upcycle mixed waste or a fraction of waste into**
 391 **marketable chemicals.**

392

393 4.3. Configuration and boundaries of a CIWMS

394 **A CIWMS should encompass the subsystems that connect the transformation of raw**
 395 **materials into waste with the waste treatment subsystems, so that the consequences of the**

396 **recirculation of the materials into the upstream subsystems can be fully accounted for.** A
397 CIWMS that relies to a lesser extent on the consumption of virgin raw materials would result
398 from the connection of the upstream subsystems with those of a traditional linear IWMS, as
399 shown in Figure 3. As many transport subsystems as necessary should be added to the system
400 depicted in Figure 3 for each particular case under study. From an LCA perspective, the
401 subsystems 0-2, which comprise the upstream and midstream processes, constitute the
402 background system of the model, whereas the remaining downstream subsystems, which
403 concern those processes under the control of the decision-maker (Frischknecht, 1998), belong
404 to the foreground system.

405

406 These system boundaries intend to capture the whole life cycle of the materials that compose
407 waste, including the stages concerning the consumption of the services derived from the
408 transformation of the natural resources extracted from the ecosystems. Once consumed, some
409 products such as food or cosmetics leave the system as air emissions or wastewater. On the
410 other hand, many products like textiles and furniture provide a service for a time period without
411 being consumed. It is worth mentioning that the primary raw materials delivered by

412

413

Figure 3. Configuration and boundaries of a CIWMS (*single fitting image*)

414 subsystem 0 cannot be compared to the secondary materials produced in subsystem 6 on a mass
415 basis; the comparison must be based on the functions provided by those materials. For instance,
416 1 kg of primary aluminum might not be functionally equivalent to 1 kg of recycled aluminum,
417 because of their different chemical composition and physical properties.

418

419 Figure 4 illustrates the exchanges between a CIWMS and the surrounding ecosystems, and
420 how a CIWMS is capable of transforming one type of environmental burden (waste) into a
421 resource that might displace the consumption of virgin resources that would provide the same
422 function.

423

424 **Figure 4.** Overview of the exchanges between a CIWMS and the ecosystems

425

426 The scope of a CIWMS that manages mixed MSW is so broad that the only systems within
427 the technosphere that it might be related to are the wastewater and the industrial waste treatment
428 systems. Those systems are outside the scope of the study of the CIWMS shown in Figure 3
429 and thus, the consequences of the decisions affecting those systems will not be considered.

430

431 *4.4. Link between industrial symbiosis and CIWMSs*

432 According to Chertow (2000), industrial symbiosis engages traditionally separate industries
433 in a collective approach to competitive advantage involving physical exchange of materials,

434 energy, water, and/or by-products. The keys to industrial symbiosis are collaboration and the
435 synergistic possibilities offered by geographic proximity. Thus, the proposed CIWMS is
436 analogous to an industrial symbiotic systems, in the sense that a resource exchange network
437 can be established. Nonetheless, although industrial symbiotic systems could play a major role
438 in the circular economy, the concept of a CIWMS is much broader; it is not restricted to nearby
439 industrial systems, but it also includes waste managers, consumers and the supply chains. That
440 is to say, not all the materials within a CIWMS are reintroduced into the production cycles
441 because of an agreement between companies.

442

443 Hence, the generic methodological approaches proposed in the literature to assess the
444 performance of industrial symbiotic systems (Martin et al., 2015; Mattila et al., 2012) should
445 not be, a priori, extended to CIWMSs.

446

447 *4.5. Recommended tools for the analysis of CIWMSs*

448 Because of the wide range of existing technologies to manage waste, process engineers must
449 carefully study the available possibilities at the design phase of a CIWMS. The superstructure
450 that might emerge after considering process integration could be quite complex. Thus, the
451 selection of the optimum configuration of the system is not a trivial matter, and it might require
452 mathematical programming techniques. Moreover, since the chemical composition of waste
453 will determine the type of processes that it can be subjected to, it can be concluded that **the**
454 **design of a CIWMS should be based on mathematical programming and Material Flow**
455 **Analysis (MFA)**, so that the circularity of materials is warranted. The combination of these
456 tools with scenario analysis techniques that assess the consequences of changes in waste

457 composition and quantities or possible technological improvements, could be a valid strategy
458 to account for the dynamic variables that might fluctuate during the studied time horizon.

459

460 On the other hand, the assessment of the performance of a CIWMS must analyze all its
461 sustainability dimensions. The sustainability criteria regarding the economic and social
462 dimensions of CIWMSs are at least as important as the environmental aspects and must be
463 likewise assessed; nonetheless, they will not be deeply discussed in this Critical Review.

464

465

466 **5. Methodologies applied in the literature**

467

468 Regarding the methodological approaches reported to be applied in the literature, Chang et
469 al. (2011) and Juul et al. (2013) classified the system analysis tools that have the potential to
470 assist in the design of IWMSs and the decision-making processes as:

- 471 i) System engineering models, which focus on supporting the design of the system. These
472 are simulation models, optimization models, forecasting models, cost-benefit analysis
473 or multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM).
- 474 ii) System assessment tools. They focus on assessing how an existing system performs.
475 LCA, MFA and risk assessment are examples of such tools.

476

477 Coupling these two types of methodologies is recommended not only because it will lead to
478 a better understanding of the IWMS (Pires et al., 2011c), but also because the sustainability
479 analysis of an IWMS requires an integrated approach; the applied methodologies should

480 complement each other so that all the sustainability dimensions can be properly evaluated and
481 the economic, environmental and social objectives are balanced.

482

483 Another strategy that has been suggested to support the decision-making process is taking a
484 participatory approach. This can be done by either asking multiple stakeholders to participate
485 in the analysis (Blengini et al., 2012), or by applying a game-theoretic approach that seeks the
486 fair distribution of benefits and costs (Karmperis et al., 2013).

487

488 The methodological approaches applied in the 77 reviewed papers are shown in Figure 5.
489 Whereas over one third of the reviewed papers focus solely on the environmental impacts
490 associated with the IWMS (all of them by means of LCA), only one study relies solely on an
491 economic assessment, based on Life Cycle Costing (LCC) (Massarutto et al., 2011). More
492 information on the application of LCC to waste management systems can be found in Martinez-
493 Sanchez et al.'s paper (2015).

494

495 Over one fifth of the reviewed studies assessed more than one sustainability dimension. A
496 few papers (Chang et al., 2012; Levis et al., 2013; Levis et al., 2014; Martinez-Sanchez et al.,
497 2017; Münster et al., 2015; Tabata et al., 2011), combine the LCA methodology and
498 optimization techniques to broaden the scope of the study and include other sustainability
499 criteria. Mirdar-Haridani et al. (2017) combined optimization and social LCA. Multi-objective
500 optimization, applied in some of the reviewed papers (Chang et al., 2012; Chang and Lin, 2013;
501 Santibañez-Aguilar et al., 2013; Santibañez-Aguilar et al., 2015; Srivastava and Nema, 2012;
502 Vadenbo et al., 2014a; Vadenbo et al., 2014b), is possibly the most adequate technique to take
503 into account all the sustainability criteria. Oppositely, other authors (Menikpura et al., 2012;

504 Tulokhonova and Ulanova, 2013) combined LCA with a set of indicators to account for the
 505 other sustainability dimensions of an IWMS.

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Figure 5. Methodological approaches applied in the reviewed studies

516

(2-column fitting image)

517

518 On the other hand, MFA and/or Substance Flow Analysis (SFA) enable to explicitly consider
 519 the waste characteristics and thus help provide a more detailed description of the system under
 520 study and track each waste fraction throughout the system. Additionally, Energy Flow Analysis
 521 (EFA), which was applied in two studies (Herva et al., 2014; Tonini et al., 2014), might prove
 522 useful to determine the most suitable valorization treatment to each waste fraction.

523

524 So far, the theoretical framework required to combine LCA, multi-objective optimization
 525 and MFA techniques has only been described by Vadenbo et al. (Vadenbo et al., 2014a;
 526 Vadenbo et al., 2014b) although the methodology was not applied to an IWMS.

527

528

529 **6. Hot topics**

530

531 The most discussed methodological aspects in the reviewed studies and the challenges and
532 possibilities of their application to the design and assessment of CIWMSs are presented in this
533 section aiming at providing some helpful and critical insights into the development of a
534 theoretical framework for the analysis of CIWMSs.

535

536 *6.1. Accounting for waste prevention*

537 Wastage of goods and products is a tremendous global challenge; taking the food supply and
538 consumption chains as an example, around one third of the food produced for human
539 consumption worldwide is currently lost or wasted (FAO, 2013).

540

541 Waste prevention stands at the top of the waste management hierarchy, as a strategy to be
542 implemented in the life cycle stage prior to waste generation that seeks to minimize the
543 depletion of natural resources and its subsequent environmental burdens. The term *waste*
544 *prevention* refers to any measures taken before a substance, material or product become waste,
545 that reduce: a) the quantity of waste, b) the adverse impacts of the generated waste and c) the
546 content of harmful substances in materials and products (EP and EC, 2008).

547

548 Nevertheless, the analysis of waste prevention activities in the framework of LCA has not
549 been normalized yet; only a few studies outline the methodological steps to follow (Cleary,
550 2010; Gentil et al., 2011; Nessi et al., 2013), concurring that this is an active area of research.

551

552 LCA models of waste management typically calculate the environmental burdens on a waste
553 mass basis. This is the most straightforward option to choose the functional unit. However, it
554 makes this approach inadequate for the comparison of scenarios including waste prevention
555 strategies, given that the amount of waste produced varies among them (Ekvall et al., 2007).
556 Moreover, these models usually rely on the “zero burden approach”, which does not include
557 the upstream processes within the system boundaries because it is assumed that their primary
558 function is not to produce waste and thus none of the environmental burdens generated in the
559 upstream processes are associated with it. Nonetheless, if different amounts of waste are
560 produced in each scenario, the zero burden approach cannot be considered because the
561 contribution of the upstream processes to the overall environmental impacts of the system will
562 differ (JRC, 2011). Consequently, **a proper methodological approach to deal with waste
563 prevention activities from a life cycle perspective should define:**

- 564 **i) A functional unit that accounts for the amount of waste prevented.**
- 565 **ii) System boundaries that include the upstream processes involved in waste
566 generation.**

567

568 Another issue that must be considered when waste prevention activities are being accounted
569 for is the allocation procedure of the environmental impacts among the products or services
570 delivered by the IWMS. Applying the direct substitution approach in order to avoid allocation
571 among several products is not recommended, given that negative results might be obtained,
572 leading to the erroneous conclusion that a greater amount of waste leads to less environmental
573 impacts (Giugliano et al., 2011).

574

575 Cleary (2010) recommends an attributional approach with system expansion to account for
576 the upstream processes associated with waste production, arguing that a consequential
577 approach does not consider waste prevention as a waste management strategy functionally
578 equivalent to the others in the waste management hierarchy, since no environmental burdens
579 are attributed to waste prevention activities; that is to say, it simply quantifies the consequences
580 of reducing the waste inputs in the system. Only Gentil et al. (2011) claim to apply a
581 consequential LCA model. These authors expand the system boundaries to the upstream
582 processes related to the waste generation processes, although they acknowledge that the
583 cascading effects of waste prevention should have been further assessed.

584

585 All of the above mentioned studies define the functional unit as the sum of the waste managed
586 through conventional methods and the amount of waste prevented, although nuances in the
587 applied approach can be found among the studies.

588

589 *6.2. Quantifying biogenic carbon*

590 Whether biogenic CO₂ emissions are considered neutral or an environmental burden to an
591 IWMS will have a significant influence on the results and conclusions drawn from the analysis.
592 Since studies relying on different assumptions are hard to compare, it is imperative to
593 standardize this matter, not only within the waste management sector.

594

595 The EPA (2017) defines biogenic CO₂ emissions as CO₂ emissions related to the natural
596 carbon cycle, as well as those resulting from the combustion, harvest, digestion, fermentation,
597 decomposition, or processing of biologically based materials. It is worth remarking that the
598 origin of fossil fuels, produced millions of years ago, is also biological (DOE, 2017).

599

600 The first difficulty that arises when calculating the carbon footprint of a given IWMS is the
601 differentiation between biogenic and fossil carbon. A rigorous MFA should be performed in
602 order to trace back the carbon source and identify the carbon sinks. Carbon (biogenic or not)
603 may be released as an environmental burden or remain in the anthroposphere, in any of the
604 following forms:

- 605 i) Emissions to the atmosphere. In the presence of oxygen, carbon is oxidized to CO₂.
606 Under anaerobic conditions carbon is reduced to CH₄.
- 607 ii) Wastewater pollution and landfill leachate wherein carbon is present in a variety of
608 organic compounds.
- 609 iii) Sequestered carbon in landfills or in soil amendment products (compost and
610 digestate).

611

612 It must be highlighted that the distinction between an environmental burden and the
613 accumulation of a substance in the IWMS under study is often unclear; the system boundaries
614 need to be precisely established at the definition of the scope of the work.

615

616 Within an efficiently designed IWMS water is not considered a final carbon sink. After the
617 adequate treatment, the carbon present in the leachate leaves the liquid phase as CO₂ or CH₄
618 (Wang et al., 2014), whereas the carbon in wastewater is distributed between the gaseous
619 emissions and the sludge (Rodriguez-Garcia et al., 2012), being the latter subsequently treated
620 as solid waste. Even though Griffith et al. (2009) estimate that up to 25% of the carbon content
621 in wastewater is of fossil origin, it is widely assumed that the totality of carbon is biogenic, and
622 thus it is typically not accounted for (Rodriguez-Garcia et al., 2012).

623

624 Although emissions from leachate treatments are estimated in some of the reviewed papers
625 (Chang et al., 2012; Manfredi et al., 2011), none of them made express reference to the carbon
626 source. The reviewed articles that accounted for biogenic CO₂ are shown in Table 1. The
627 procedure followed to determine the carbon origin is not clearly stated in many cases. Whereas
628 Tabata et al. (2011) and Vergara et al. (2011) consider that biogenic CO₂ is derived from the
629 biogenic fraction of waste, only Manfredi et al. (2011) and Turner et al. (2016) explicitly
630 consider the fraction of biogenic carbon in the input waste.

631

632 Regarding the stored carbon in landfills and the carbon emissions to the atmosphere, for the
633 specific case in which an LCA is performed with the objective of comparing different scenarios
634 but there is no interest in knowing the values of their individual carbon footprints, Christensen
635 et al.(2009) proved that, provided that the assumptions concerning biogenic CO₂ emissions and
636 carbon sequestration are consistent (considering biogenic CO₂ emissions either neutral or not
637 neutral) and the system boundaries are clearly established, the emission ranking of scenarios
638 remains the same.

639

640 As can be seen in Table 1, biogenic CO₂ emissions are assigned a GWP factor (expressed as
641 kg of equivalent CO₂ per kg of emitted CO₂) of zero in most studies, which implies that no
642 environmental impacts in terms of climate change potential are attributed to them. Applying
643 this GWP is analogous to expanding the system boundaries to include the upstream processes
644 of photosynthesis. Thus, unless biogenic CO₂ is being stored, the CO₂ that is captured during
645 the growth of biomass and comes into the system, is balanced with the biogenic CO₂ that leaves
646 the system, achieving carbon neutrality. For the sake of coherence, a negative GWP must be

647 assigned to the carbon that is captured in the photosynthetic processes and remains sequestered
 648 in the system. Nonetheless, as Vergara et al. (2011) point out, by applying this procedure only
 649 the environmental benefits of the upstream processes are being taken into account, disregarding
 650 their environmental burdens. As a consequence, this approach might lead to higher
 651 environmental credits than burdens, entailing that landfills and soil amendment products
 652 contribute to climate change mitigation (Turner et al., 2016).

653

654 **Table 1.** GWP and other methodological considerations regarding biogenic carbon in the
 655 reviewed papers

	Biogenic CO ₂		Stored biogenic carbon		Specified carbon source?	Zero burden approach?
	Value	Unit	Value	Unit		
Aghajani et al. (2016)	0	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	-	-	No	Yes
Blengini et al. (2012)	1	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	-1	Unspecified	No	Yes
Chang et al. (2012)	0	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	-	-	No	Yes
Manfredi et al. (2011)	0	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	-44/12	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg C	Yes	Yes
Minoglou et al. (2013)	0	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	-	-	No	Yes
Tabata (2011)	0	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	-	-	Yes	Yes
Turner et al. (2016)	0	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	0 or -44/12	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg C	Yes	Yes

Vergara et al. (2011)	0	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	-1	Unspecified	Yes	No
	1	kg CO ₂ -eq/kg CO ₂	0	Unspecified	Yes	Yes

656

657

658 To correct this incoherence, the carbon flows that connect the system to the environment
659 (primarily as CO₂ and CH₄) must be inventoried. **If the system boundaries are expanded to**
660 **include the upstream processes, once the elemental composition of the waste and products**
661 **is known, the incoming carbon flows can be easily calculated: every mole of biogenic**
662 **carbon present in the products, waste and emissions originates from a mole of CO₂ that**
663 **was absorbed by biomass in the photosynthetic process.** Afterwards, the carbon flows that
664 come into the system must be subtracted from the carbon flows that leave the studied system.

665

666 This systematic approach allows applying the same GWP (1 kg CO₂-eq/kg CO₂) to CO₂
667 emissions from scenarios with different system boundaries, regardless of the CO₂ origin.

668

669 The proposed procedure, which relies on the waste composition provided by the MFA,
670 **ensures that the CO₂ removed from the atmosphere, whose carbon eventually leaves the**
671 **system as CH₄, is accounted for. The studies** compiled in Table 1 **make no express**
672 **reference to a correction in the GWP of biogenic CH₄,** when in reality CH₄ constitutes a
673 significant fraction of the outlet stream of some technologies that process biogenic waste, such
674 as anaerobic digestion.

675

676 *6.3. Accounting for uncertainty*

677 Models aiming at describing complex systems carry a level of uncertainty whose effect on
678 the outcome might be hard to predict without the right methodology. There are plenty of
679 sources of uncertainty within an IWMS, such as waste composition, the efficiency of the
680 treatment processes, the substitution ratio of virgin materials or the effect that the seasonal
681 changes in weather may have on the waste degradation rate. For a detailed compilation of
682 uncertainty sources, the reader should refer to Clavreul et al. (2012). However, **the paramount**
683 **variable with which uncertainty is associated**, regardless of the complexity of the model, **is**
684 **waste composition.**

685

686 As Laurent et al. (2014) pinpointed in their review, LCA studies do not usually account for
687 waste composition very accurately. This asseveration could be further extended to waste
688 management models in general, even though waste composition will determine the results of
689 the subsequent analysis, simulation or optimization, given that the available treatment options
690 and the type and amount of emissions resulting from the different waste treatment alternatives
691 strongly depend on the elemental composition of waste. This is the reason coupling MFA with
692 other analysis tools is the precursor to identifying the optimal configuration of an IWMS.
693 Nevertheless, adequately characterizing the waste composition is a difficult task because of the
694 heterogeneity of the material flows, and it might require complex statistical analysis. Thus,
695 representative data of the average waste composition inevitably brings uncertainty into the
696 model.

697

698 The elements that are excluded from the analysis without a clear justification also represent
699 a source of uncertainty. For instance, the environmental impacts related to capital goods might

700 have a significant influence on the results of an LCA (Brogaard and Christensen, 2016), but
701 they are often not modeled (Chi et al., 2015; Laurent et al., 2014; Suwan and Gheewala, 2012).

702

703 Stochastic modeling, which relies on the propagation of probability distributions, is the most
704 frequently deployed methodology to consider the effect of uncertainties on the LCA results,
705 although scenario analysis is more commonly applied for the LCA of waste management
706 (Clavreul et al., 2012). Sensitivity analysis to investigate the effects of a change on an
707 assumption or the value of a parameter are routinely performed in many of the reviewed studies
708 (Blengini et al., 2012; Boesch et al., 2014; Bovea et al., 2010; Chi et al., 2015; Cleary, 2012;
709 Eriksson et al., 2005; Fiorentino et al., 2015; Fruergaard and Astrup, 2011; Giugliano et al.,
710 2011; Jeswani and Azapagic, 2016; Koci and Trecakova, 2011; Koroneos and Nanaki, 2012;
711 Manfredi et al., 2011; Pressley et al., 2014; Rigamonti et al., 2009; Song et al., 2013; Tonini
712 and Astrup, 2012; Tonini et al., 2013; Turner et al., 2016; Vergara et al., 2011; Wang et al.,
713 2015). Massarutto et al. (2011) also carried out a sensitivity analysis in their LCC analysis.
714 Notwithstanding only three of the above-mentioned studies (Pressley et al., 2014; Tonini and
715 Astrup, 2012; Tonini et al., 2013) analyzed the impact that different waste compositions would
716 have on the results.

717

718 Hanandeh and El-Zein (2010) considered the uncertainty related to the input waste
719 composition, among other parameters. Comparing the results of the stochastic model of an
720 IMWS with those of a deterministic model, they found that when uncertainty is taken into
721 account, the environmental burdens of one of the studied impact categories became
722 environmental credits, proving that the uncertainty of the data in their case study was definitely
723 not negligible. However, Clavreul et al. (2012) claim that probability distributions, which are

724 oftentimes dependent on incomplete information, should be applied cautiously. Instead, they
725 proposed a systematic sequential approach to quantify uncertainty in LCA models of waste
726 management systems that comprises a number of complementary methodologies for
727 uncertainty analysis.

728

729 Regarding the quantification of uncertainty in the models aiming at optimizing IWMSs, two
730 methodologies can be differentiated in the reviewed literature:

731 i) After the initial optimization of the objective functions a sensitivity analysis is
732 performed to check the effect of a change in the input parameters or the assumptions
733 made on the optimal solution. Tabata et al. (2011), Tan et al. (2014) and Thikimoanh
734 et al. (2015) apply this methodology.

735 ii) A methodology to quantify uncertainty is embedded in the model or the optimization
736 technique. Table 2 compiles the modeling and optimization methodologies applied
737 for that purpose in the reviewed studies.

738

739 As can be seen in Table 2, some studies apply a combination of techniques. Interval
740 programming, in which uncertainties are expressed as interval values, is the most common
741 programming technique to quantify uncertainty. Stochastic and fuzzy programming are also
742 popular; the difference between them is that in stochastic programming uncertainty is modeled
743 through discrete or continuous probability functions, whereas fuzzy programming considers
744 random parameters as fuzzy numbers and constraints are treated as fuzzy sets (Sahinidis, 2004).

745

746 Finally, an approach to quantify uncertainty within MCDM models was proposed by Pires et
747 al. (2011a). They developed a MCDM framework that integrates an interval-valued fuzzy

748 method with the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) and the technique for order performance by
 749 similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS) in order to help decision-makers prioritize waste
 750 management scenarios.

751

752 **Table 2.** Methodologies to quantify the effects of uncertainty in the reviewed optimization
 753 models

	Fuzzy programming	Stochastic programming	Interval programming	Factorial design	Minimax regret analysis
Cui et al. (2011)			x		x
Chang et al. (2013)	x				
Dai et al. (2011)			x		
Li and Chen (2011)	x	x	x		
Srivastava et al. (2011)	x				
Wang et al. (2012)	x	x	x		
Zhai et al. (2016)			x	x	
Zhou et al. (2016)		x			
Zhu and Huang (2011)		x			

754

755 The extensive amount of methodologies developed to account for uncertainty makes it hard
 756 for the non-experts to choose the most appropriate one for the analysis of their IWMS. Two

757 trends have been observed in the literature: the performance of sensitivity analysis and the
758 combination of several methodologies. The former risks not capturing the complexity of the
759 model, while the latter may become a time consuming process that considerably increases the
760 researchers' effort.

761

762 In any case, **a meaningful uncertainty analysis must be based on the correct**
763 **identification of the parameters and assumptions that will bring uncertainty into the**
764 **model**, which are not always clearly listed in the reviewed studies.

765

766 *6.4. Dynamic modeling*

767 Most of the reviewed models, with the exception of multi-period optimization models (Cui
768 et al., 2011; Dai et al., 2011; Levis et al., 2013; Levis et al., 2014; Li and Chen, 2011; Mirdar-
769 Haridani et al., 2017; Srivastava and Nema, 2011; Srivastava and Nema, 2012; Tan et al., 2014;
770 Zhai et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2016; Zhu and Huang, 2011), describe static IWMSs that do not
771 account for changes in the system variables throughout time. Oppositely, multi-period
772 optimization models assume that the constraints and the parameters remain constant within a
773 given time period, although they may differ between different stages. Hence, in spite of being
774 time dependent, the outputs of these models are not a function of time, but a function of the
775 time period. In fact, models introducing time series have been classified as *quasi-dynamic*
776 (Lundie et al., 2007), under the argument that the results of one period do not determine the
777 results of the next period. The implementation of dynamic models whose outputs are a function
778 of time would bring a higher degree of complexity into the analysis; for instance, modeling the
779 behavior of markets throughout time would add realism to an LCA, but because of the large
780 data requirements, it is not usually considered a feasible option (Lundie et al., 2007).

781

782 Thus, the definition of time stages appears to be the most straightforward and practical route
783 to account for the time-dependent changes in the system, such as the need to manage obsolete
784 goods after they have provided the expected service. The shorter the established time periods,
785 the more reliable the model will be. **The time periods should be established so that the**
786 **seasonal variations in waste composition are accounted for.** Of the reviewed studies, only
787 Levis et al. (2014) took into account the changes in waste composition in the studied time
788 period. If the study aims at quantifying the environmental impacts and the consumption of
789 natural resources of the system, successive LCAs should be performed for each time period in
790 which the input waste composition varies. Accordingly, different functional units referring to
791 each specific time period should be defined.

792

793 The seasonal changes in waste composition (proved for example by Castrillón et al. (2013))
794 pose a challenge to the design of CIWMSs, given that they must be flexible enough to adjust
795 to the changes in the feed composition. Furthermore, since manufacturers cannot count on a
796 steady supply of secondary materials, the fluctuations in waste composition hamper the shift
797 to a circular economy.

798

799 It is important not to confuse the duration of the supply of goods and services provided by
800 the system, which is identified by the functional unit, with the time horizon of the LCA (JRC,
801 2011), which is the time length during which the flows that connect the IWMS with the
802 environment are accounted for. Additionally, the selected time horizon determines the value of
803 the characterization factors used to calculate the contribution of the different substances exiting
804 the system to each of the impact categories studied on the LCA (JRC, 2010). Thus, the time

805 horizon must be long enough to include all the relevant emissions to the environment. This
806 guideline is of particular interest for modeling landfills, since their emissions may prevail for
807 a long time in the order of thousands of years (Finnveden, 1999).

808

809 For the defined time period in which a CIWMS is analyzed, certain waste fractions might
810 travel within the system for a number of times; depending on the time at which the system is
811 being described, some materials may be part of the waste or the products. In fact, the products
812 into which a material is transformed might even be different if they undergo an open-loop
813 recycling process. A methodology to calculate the average number of times a material is used
814 was proposed by Yamada et al. (2006).

815

816 **The disparities in the material flows within a given time period can only be solved by**
817 **assuming that the model concerning each time period is a steady-state model;** that is to
818 say, that the incoming natural resources and the flows of waste and products within the system
819 are constant and homogeneously distributed along the studied time period. Following this
820 methodology, materials should be counted as both waste and products as many times as cycles
821 they describe within the system in the defined time period.

822

823

824 **7. Application of the cradle-to-cradle approach**

825

826 The boundaries of a CIWMS do not enable to implement the traditional linear cradle-to-
827 grave LCA; thus, a cradle-to-cradle approach must be applied. In this section the adjustments
828 to the LCA scope that this new perspective requires will be discussed, focusing on the modeling

829 framework, the multi-functionality problem and the definition of the functional unit, all of
830 which are intrinsically related to one another and will be determined by the goal and scope
831 definition.

832

833 *7.1. Goal and scope definition*

834 The goal of the LCA of a given CIWMS might differ among studies, which makes it hard, if
835 not impossible, to compare their results. The proposed methodology discussed in this section
836 will be coherent with this goal: to identify possible improvements in the design of a CIWMS
837 wherein waste prevention activities are implemented, so that its environmental impacts and its
838 consumption of natural resources can be minimized. Hence, the analysis is intended to assist
839 the decision-makers in the design of a CIWMS.

840

841 *7.2. Multi-functionality problem*

842 The LCA practitioner might come across a multi-functionality problem: how to allocate the
843 environmental impacts between all the functions that the system supplies if the further
844 subdivision of the subsystems that configure the CIWMS cannot be applied to avoid allocation,
845 because of the interconnection between them. To deal with this multi-functionality problem,
846 two strategies, which depend on the selected modeling approach, can be applied (Finnveden et
847 al., 2009; ISO 14044, 2006): system expansion or allocation. According to ISO 14044 (2006),
848 system expansion should be deployed wherever possible in order to avoid partitioning the
849 environmental burdens.

850

851 Most studies analyzing IWMSs apply the direct substitution (also called avoided burden)
852 method (Abeliotis et al., 2012; Al-Salem et al., 2014; Evangelisti et al., 2015; Antonopoulos,

853 et al., 2013; Belboom et al., 2013; Blengini et al., 2012; Boesch et al., 2014; Bovea et al., 2010;
854 Chi et al., 2015; Dong et al., 2014; Eriksson et al., 2014; Evangelisti et al., 2015; Fiorentino et
855 al., 2015; Fruergaard and Astrup, 2011; Gentil et al., 2011; Giugliano et al., 2011; Jeswani and
856 Azapagic, 2016; Manfredi et al., 2011; Menikpura et al., 2012; Menikpura et al., 2013;
857 Montejo, et al., 2013; Pandyaswargo et al., 2012; Pires et al., 2011b; Pressley et al., 2014; Rada
858 et al., 2014; Rigamonti et al., 2013; Suwan and Gheewala, 2012; Tonini and Astrup, 2012;
859 Tonini et al., 2013; Tulokhonova and Ulanova, 2013; Tunesi, 2011; Turner et al., 2016;
860 Vergara et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2015); they consider that the primary aim of their system is
861 to treat waste, and they expand the system boundaries to include within the system the other
862 products and services supplied, like materials and energy, and subtract their environmental
863 impacts from those of the original system. However, **a CIWMS does not operate under the**
864 **assumption that waste needs to be treated in order to minimize its negative impacts, but**
865 **valorized, so that the consumption of natural resources is reduced.**

866

867 *7.2.1 Functions of a CIWMS*

868 According to the system boundaries set in Figure 3, the functions fulfilled by a CIWMS are
869 twofold:

- 870 i) To supply the services that society demands, regardless of the origin of the raw
871 materials.
- 872 ii) To exploit the maximum amount of the generated waste, by either producing new
873 products from it or recovering its energy, with the ultimate goal of minimizing the
874 consumption of natural resources.

875

876 The second function is a consequence of the first one, and the first one can be partially
877 achieved due to the accomplishment of the second function. However, if waste upgrading and
878 energy recovery processes were not implemented, the supply of the services demanded by
879 society could still meet the demand, relying solely on the extraction of natural resources. Thus,
880 it can be agreed that the primary function of a CIWMS is waste exploitation.

881

882 According to the definition of the system functions, it is not necessary to disaggregate any
883 of them by the type of services and products provided in order to solve the multi-functionality
884 problem. This way, the uncertainty brought into the model by the choice of the allocation
885 procedure is reduced. Moreover, the problem of allocation in open-loop recycling, which is a
886 recurrent discussion in the LCA literature (Ekvall, 2000; Ekvall and Finnveden, 2001;
887 Finnveden, 1999; Yamada et al., 2006; Shen et al., 2010), is avoided.

888

889 7.2.2. System expansion approach

890 If the LCA practitioners are interested in analyzing the overall environmental impacts of the
891 whole system, the system expansion approach must be followed. The studied CIWMS should
892 be compared to a functionally equivalent system whose functions are provided by alternative
893 subsystems (Finnveden, 1999); for instance, a linear IWMS that depends exclusively on virgin
894 raw materials. The environmental benefits of the complete CIWMS could be estimated as the
895 difference in the environmental impacts of the linear and circular IWMSs.

896

897 If on the contrary, the study aims at investigating the environmental impacts derived from
898 the primary function of the CIWMS, the direct substitution or avoided burden approach could
899 be applied by expanding the system boundaries to include alternative subsystems responsible

900 for the secondary function, based entirely on virgin raw materials. Their environmental impacts
901 should be subsequently calculated and subtracted from the environmental impacts of the
902 studied CIWMS. Accordingly, the resulting environmental impacts are assumed to be due to
903 the primary function of the system. This might result in overall negative environmental impacts
904 and, as a consequence, the system could be mistaken for an environmental burdens sink.

905

906 If system expansion is applied, a choice between marginal and average data must be made to
907 model the system functions. Marginal data is used to model systems whose outputs change in
908 response to decisions regarding the life cycle of the system under study, for example a decrease
909 in the demand for the electricity produced from natural gas as a consequence of the supply of
910 electricity from waste-to-energy processes. Average data, on the other hand, represents the
911 mean data in a region; the average electricity mix refers to the grid mix of that region, and it
912 does not reflect any changes in fuel consumption because of the changes in the electricity
913 demand. Although average data might lack accuracy, it is more appropriate if the effects that
914 the decisions taken have on the surrounding systems are not certain. The selection of the data
915 is closely related to the LCA modeling framework applied. Whereas “attributional LCA
916 focuses on describing environmentally relevant physical flows to and from a life cycle,
917 consequential LCA aims at describing how the environmentally relevant physical flows to and
918 from the life cycle will change in response to possible decisions” (Finnveden et al., 2009).

919

920 *7.2.3. Allocation approach*

921 Heijungs and Guinée (2007) are firm advocates of allocation procedures because the
922 assumptions on which the direct substitution approach is based are likely to introduce
923 considerable uncertainty into the model. Whereas they recognize that the allocation approach

924 is subject to essentially arbitrary allocation factors, they argue that it is extremely hard to
925 predict what system would be affected if the secondary function of the studied system was
926 meant to replace one of the functions of another system, and up to what extent the
927 environmental impacts caused by the other system would be avoided. Although the selection
928 of a 100% substitution ratio is common, several authors suggest that a complete displacement
929 is unlikely (Geyer et al., 2016; Vadenbo et al., 2016; Zink et al., 2016; Zink et al., 2017).

930

931 In addition to that, if the substituted function was produced in a multi-functional system, the
932 system boundaries would have to be further expanded until mono-functional systems were
933 found, significantly increasing the complexity and the uncertainty of the system. Ekvall and
934 Finnveden (2001) also acknowledged the importance of the uncertainty caused by system
935 expansion; they stated that system expansion is an adequate procedure to solve the multi-
936 functionality problem as long as data for the competing production of the secondary function
937 is available, and the data uncertainties are not too large, which agrees with the guidelines of
938 ISO 14044 (2006).

939

940 This argument can be easily extrapolated to the case of a CIWMS aiming at valorizing MSW.
941 The resources transformation subsystem, responsible for the secondary function of a CIWMS,
942 comprises many production subsystems; modeling the alternative processes relying on virgin
943 raw materials would bring multiple sources of uncertainty into the model, not to mention that
944 it would be an extremely time consuming task.

945

946 If an allocation procedure is selected to solve the multi-functionality problem, it must be
947 borne in mind that except when physical causal relationships are deployed as a basis for

948 allocation, the property according to which the allocation is performed depends entirely on the
949 choice of the LCA practitioner.

950

951 The chemical composition of the flows within a CIWMS, determined by the MFA, is a valid
952 causal criterion to allocate the input-specific environmental impacts. However, given that the
953 composition of the recycled materials should be, a priori, identical to the composition of the
954 virgin materials, this criterion could only be applied in the cases wherein either the recycled
955 materials carry pollutants accumulated in the recycling process, or certain materials cannot be
956 recycled and thus the environmental impacts derived from the processing of those materials
957 are due to the incoming virgin materials into the system. Furthermore, the environmental
958 impacts caused by the process specific emissions, such as dioxins and furans produced in the
959 incineration processes (Margallo et al., 2014), which are dependent on the operating conditions
960 and the applied technologies, cannot be allocated according to the chemical composition of the
961 input flows.

962

963 Hence, a different allocation factor that enables to partition all the environmental impacts
964 between the system functions must be defined. There are basically two types of approaches to
965 perform the allocation of environmental impacts in the cases wherein causal relationships
966 cannot be found, those relying on a physical parameter, such as mass or volume, and those that
967 are based on socioeconomic criteria. Even though both approaches are internally consistent as
968 long as the selected physical property or socioeconomic indicator is also applied to quantify
969 the performance of the system and used to calculate the functional unit, different results will
970 be obtained for different allocation factors, and they might show opposite trends. Therefore,

971 the choice of the allocation factor should never be made based on an arbitrary decision, it
972 should respond to the goal and scope of the LCA instead (Pelletier et al., 2015).

973

974 One of the reasons for not including socioeconomic parameters in the LCA is that if more
975 than one of the sustainability dimensions (economy, environment and society) are studied
976 jointly, some of the trends in the results might be overlooked. For instance, the objective of the
977 study of the carbon footprint of a CIWMS wherein the functional unit is defined as the revenues
978 generated in a given time period, could be to detect what changes in the configuration of the
979 CIWMS would result in a minimization of the ratio kg CO₂-eq/€. Expressing the results as a
980 ratio between those two variables might make it harder to identify if only the environmental
981 impacts, only the economic revenues or both the environmental impacts and the economic
982 revenues are improved as a consequence of a change in the technical parameters of the system.

983

984 Moreover, since the goal of the LCA was defined at the beginning of this section from a
985 technical perspective, making no reference to economic criteria, a physical parameter is more
986 appropriate to allocate the environmental impacts. **The different material fractions emerging
987 from the materials sorting subsystem will be transformed into a variety of goods and
988 services, which hinders the selection of a single allocation factor based on a physical
989 property that enables to assess the multiple functions of the goods and services delivered.**
990 Nonetheless, **the mass of waste before it has been transformed into products or supplies
991 any services could be viewed as an indicator of its potential.** Hence, mass seems to be the
992 most appropriate physical parameter to perform the allocation of the environmental impacts of
993 a CIWMS.

994

995 In the context of a CIWMS, MSW is a substitute for natural resources; in particular, for raw
 996 materials. **If the amount of energy, materials and products derived from waste** that enter
 997 **SS 1 rises, the incoming raw materials** to subsystem 0 **decrease in order to maintain the**
 998 **functions delivered by the CIWMS constant.** Therefore, the allocation factor of the
 999 environmental impacts to the primary function of the system (*AF*) could be defined as the ratio
 1000 between the mass of the MSW that is valorized in subsystems 6 and 7 (*MSW_{6,7}*), and the mass
 1001 of raw materials (*RM*) and the valorized MSW, as shown in equation 1.

$$1002 \quad AF = \frac{MSW_{6,7}}{RM + MSW_{6,7}} \quad (1)$$

1003

1004 *7.2.4. Summary of approaches to solve the multi-functionality problem*

1005 The LCA practitioner should ponder the disadvantages of each approach and apply the one
 1006 that fits the best the goal of the study and the data availability. Table 3 sums up the main
 1007 disadvantages of the application of the different methodological approaches to the LCA of a
 1008 CIWMS.

1009

1010 **Table 3.** Summary of the drawbacks of alternative methodological approaches

		Attributional	Consequential	
Allocation	By mass	a	Not applicable	
	By economic value	a, b		
System expansion	Average data	Comparison	Not applicable	
		Substitution		d, e
	Marginal data	Comparison	Not applicable	c
		Substitution		d

1011 a. Consequences on the exported functions of alternative systems not considered

- 1012 b. Hard to separately identify the response of revenues and environmental impacts to
1013 changes in the IWMS
- 1014 c. Environmental impacts of the overall system; specific environmental impacts of the
1015 primary function not known
- 1016 d. Negative results not coherent with waste prevention activities
- 1017 e. Data uncertainty modeling alternative processes

1018

1019 *7.3. Functional unit*

1020 Regarding the functional unit, it must describe the performance of the CIWMS in terms of
1021 the fulfillment of the primary function of the system; its aim is to quantify the performance of
1022 a system so that it can be used as a reference unit (ISO 14040, 2006).

1023

1024 Two thirds of the reviewed LCA studies deployed a round functional unit (1 ton or 1,000
1025 tons of MSW), which, as highlighted by Laurent et al. (2014), simply quantifies a waste flow,
1026 without describing the performance of the IWMS. On the other hand, the functional unit of
1027 several of the reviewed studies was the incoming amount of waste into the system.
1028 Notwithstanding, **the shift in the perspective of the analysis from waste (in a typical linear
1029 IWMS) to resource (in the defined CIWMS) should be reflected on the functional unit.**
1030 Therefore, since the ultimate goal of a CIWMS is to reduce the extraction of raw materials, the
1031 mass of the incoming raw materials into the system could be accounted for in the definition of
1032 the functional unit of a CIWMS.

1033

1034 Furthermore, if waste prevention activities are considered one of the targets of a CIWMS,
1035 the amount of raw materials prevented as a consequence of the waste prevention activities
1036 should also be taken into account in the definition of the functional unit, so that scenarios with
1037 and without waste prevention activities can be compared on the same basis.

1038

1039 Thus the functional unit of a CIWMS could be defined as the sum of the incoming raw
1040 materials into the system in the selected time period and in a given region plus the amount of
1041 raw materials that would have been consumed if waste prevention policies had not been
1042 implemented in that time period in that geographic area.

1043

1044 These recommendations are provided for a generic CIWMS that manages the variety of
1045 materials present in MSW. The discussion would be different if the system under study aimed
1046 at valorizing a specific type of waste and sending it back to the subsystem where it was
1047 generated. In this scenario, the selected functional unit could be a parameter different from the
1048 mass of the raw materials that reflects the precise primary function of the system.

1049

1050 Taking a CIWMS that focuses on the management of food waste as an example, its functions
1051 are to provide food for the population of a given region, and to valorize the generated organic
1052 waste into a fertilizer that is looped back into the food production subsystem. One parameter
1053 that could quantify the primary system function (waste valorization into a fertilizer) better than
1054 the incoming mass of raw materials into the system would be the area of land that is fertilized.

1055

1056

1057 **8. Conclusions**

1058

1059 Based on the insights gained in the literature review, it was concluded that some of the
1060 shortcomings that applying the current methodological approaches to a CIWMS would entail
1061 could be solved by expanding the boundaries of a traditional linear IWMS to include upstream

1062 subsystems that link the transformation of raw materials into MSW with the waste treatment
1063 subsystems. This approach is also helpful to the analysis of waste prevention activities and the
1064 quantification of the biogenic carbon present in waste.

1065

1066 Waste composition will determine the functions fulfilled by the CIWMS. A CIWMS
1067 managing mixed MSW could deliver materials, energy, nutrients and even chemicals. Because
1068 of the wide range of technologies that each waste fraction can be subjected to, mathematical
1069 programming and MFA are essential to the design of CIWMSs. However, these techniques
1070 must be combined with system assessment tools, such as LCC and LCA.

1071

1072 Unarguably, the benefits derived from the implementation of CIWMSs are due to the reduction
1073 in the consumption of natural resources. However, the economic and environmental benefits
1074 of CIWMSs are not self-evident and need to be proven by an in-depth analysis.

1075

1076 One of the challenges of performing the LCA of a given CIWMS lies on the multiplicity of
1077 materials that the system can handle, which translates into the great variety of services supplied
1078 and makes it hard to select the functional unit, which should reflect the shift in the perspective
1079 of the analysis from waste to resource.

1080

1081 Nonetheless, the main difficulty that will arise from the recommended approach will
1082 probably not stem from the integration of different methodologies, but from the upstream
1083 subsystems; considering their large size, their detailed analysis will increase the complexity of
1084 the model and the researchers' efforts needed in the modeling phase.

1085

1086

1087 **Abbreviations**

1088 Circular Integrated Waste Management System, CIWMS; Energy Flow Analysis, EFA;

1089 Integrated Waste Management System, IWMS; Life Cycle Assessment, LCA; Life Cycle

1090 Costing, LCC; Material Flow Analysis, MFA; Multi-Criteria Decision-Making, MCDM;

1091 Municipal Solid Waste, MSW; Substance Flow Analysis, SFA.

1092

1093

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1097

1098

1099

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1610 APPENDIX A

1611 **From linear to circular integrated waste**

1612 **management systems: a framework**

1613 *Selene Cobo^a, Antonio Dominguez-Ramos^b and Angel Irabien^c*

1614 ^{a,b,c}Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, University of Cantabria,

1615 Avda. los Castros s.n., Santander, 39005, Spain

1616 **^aCorresponding Author. Tel.: +34 942 20 09 31. E-mail: cobos@unican.es.**

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1625 **Table A1.** Reviewed studies and applied methodologies

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Reference	Methodology
Abeliotis et al. (2012)	LCA
Aghajani et al. (2016)	MCDM
Akbarpour et al. (2016)	Optimization
Allesch and Brunner(2014)	Review
Antonopoulos et al.(2013)	LCA
Arena and Di Gregorio (2014)	MFA and SFA
Belboom et al.(2013)	LCA
Blengini et al.(2012)	LCA
Boesch et al. (2014)	LCA
Bovea et al. (2010)	LCA
Chang et al.(2011)	Review
Chang et al.(2012)	LCA and optimization
Chang et al. (2013)	Optimization
Chi et al.(2015)	LCA
Consonni et al.(2011)	Review
Consonni and Viganò (2011)	Material and energy analysis
Cui et al.(2011)	Optimization
Dai et al.(2011)	Optimization
Eriksson and Bisailon (2011)	LCA
Eriksson et al. (2014)	LCA and financial cost calculation
Erses Yay (2015)	LCA
Falzon et al.(2013)	LCA
Fernández-Nava et al. (2014)	LCA
Fiorentino et al. (2015)	LCA
Ghiani et al. (2014)	Review

Giugliano et al. (2011)	LCA
Herva et al. (2014)	EFA, MFA and Ecological footprint
Ionescu et al. (2013)	Environmental indicators
Jovanovic et al. (2016)	LCA and MCDM
Juul et al. (2013)	Review
Karmperis et al. (2013)	Review
Koci and Trecakova (2011)	LCA
Koroneos and Nanaki (2012)	LCA
Laurent et al. (2014a, 2014b)	Review
Levis et al. (2013)	LCA and optimization
Levis et al. (2014)	LCA and optimization
Martinez-Sanchez et al. (2017)	LCA and optimization
Li and Chen (2011)	Optimization
Massarutto et al. (2011)	LCC
Menikpura et al. (2012)	LCA, economic and social assessments
Menikpura et al.(2013)	LCA
Minoglou and Komilis (2013)	Optimization
Mirdar-Harijani (2017)	Optimization and social LCA
Münster et al. (2015)	LCA and optimization
Ng et al.(2014)	Optimization
Niziolek et al. (2015)	Optimization
Pandyaswargo et al. (2012)	LCA
Pires et al. (2011a)	LCA
Pires et al. (2011b)	Review
Pressley et al. (2014)	LCA
Rada et al. (2014)	LCA
Rigamonti et al.(2013)	LCA

Rigamonti et al. (2016)	Materials recovery, energy recovery and costs indicators	1629
Sadhukhan et al.(2016)	Techno-economic analysis	1630
Santibáñez-Aguilar et al. (2013)	Optimization	1631
Santibáñez-Aguilar et al. (2015)	Optimization	1632
Satchatippavarn et al.(2016)	Optimization	1633
Song et al.(2013)	LCA	1634
Srivastava et al.(2011)	Optimization	1635
Srivastava et al.(2012)	Optimization	1636
Suwan and Gheewala (2012)	LCA	1637
Tabata et al.(2011)	LCA and optimization	1637
Tan et al. (2014)	Optimization	1638
ThiKimOanh et al. (2015)	Optimization	1639
Tonini and Astrup (2012)	LCA	1640
Tonini et al. (2013)	LCA	1641
Tonini et al. (2014)	MFA, SFA, EFA, optimization	1642
Tulokhonova and Ulanova (2013)	LCA, economic and social assessments	1643
Tunesi (2011)	LCA	1644
Vadenbo et al.(2014a, 2014b)	MFA, LCA, optimization	1645
Wang et al.(2012)	Optimization	1646
Wang et al.(2015)	LCA	1647
Zaccariello et al. (2015)	MFA and efficiency indicators	1648
Zhou et al.(2016)	Optimization	1649
Zhu and Huang (2011)	Optimization	1650
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